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AN APPROACH TO DEVELOP ADAPABLE AND ACCEPTED PRODUCTS FOR SENIORS

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes an approach for the development of adaptable products for people who are suffering from age-related disabilities. In order to fulfill the users' needs they have to be included in the product development process. Both, the functionality of the product and its acceptance can be improved by the inclusion of users. A modular product structure permits to adapt the product to the users' needs, even if these are changing due to changing disabilities or changes in the environment. The combination of these two approaches enables design engineers to create products that are both helpful and accepted.

Keywords: design for elderly people, disabilities in product development, adaption of products to disabilities

INTRODUCTION

Due to the demographic change, societies of the industrial nations have to face several problems. Not only the percentage of older people within the society, but also the number of people who need assistance in everyday life is increasing. At the same time the number of people who can provide this assistance is declining. This gap can be closed to a certain extent by technical systems. Obviously, human care and attention cannot be replaced by technical systems, but they can help to make everyday life easier. People who are suffering from disabilities benefit from using technical devices, if these are designed properly.

All products should be designed in a way that they can be used by as many people as possible. There should be no difference between disabled and able-bodied people. There are different approaches how this can be implemented in product development,

for example the approaches of inclusive design (Coleman et al., 2003) or universal design (Herwig, 2008). This particularly applies to everyday products, which are used by all people, independent of age and disabilities. This approach describes the development of aids, which are used mainly by disabled people, but it is possible to transfer it to the development of everyday products, which are used by both, disabled and able-bodied people. People who are suffering from age-related disabilities often suffer from more than one disorder. This makes the use of products, even of aids for disabled people, even more complicated. The objective of this paper is to introduce an approach that shows how to develop products that fulfill as many as possible of the seniors' needs. Therefore, the users have to be integrated into the product development process as soon as possible and participate actively. Furthermore, the approach describes the development of products that are adaptable during the useful life in order to fulfill the needs, even if they change. The focus is on needs due to age-based disabilities. Only adaptable products are able to fulfill the users' needs for a long time, when their abilities change. If the product that is used can be adapted to the changing needs, it is not necessary to buy a new one. This does not only save the users' money, but they do not have to learn to use a new product.

APPROACHES TO INTEGRATE USERS

The designers of products for seniors are often young engineers. They lack experience with disabilities and they do not know about the following difficulty in using products. But in order to develop products that fulfill the disabled users' needs, the designer has to know these needs. One possibility to close this gap is to include the future users into the product

development process. With this method, a second difficulty in the development of products for seniors can be addressed. Products for seniors are often not accepted by them, because they are stigmatizing or difficult to use. One example for a product that is difficult to use is described by Lindenberger et al. (2011). They describe hearing aids which can be operated in different modes, depending on the surrounding. But switching the mode is so difficult, that the users normally do not use this additional functionality. Newer hearing aids switch modes automatically and these devices are considered as more useful and they are used more than the older ones.

There are various approaches for the integration of users into the product development process (e.g. Kujala, 2003, Sarodnick & Brau, 2006, Hoffmann, 2007). But most of these approaches are either for the integration of users in the context of work or in the context of software development or human-computer interaction. One part of this project is to find out whether there are methods that can be transferred to the context of product development for elderly people and how this can be done. One particularity of seniors as user group is the heterogeneity in comparison with other user groups (Lang et al., 2011) as people over the age of 65 are commonly considered as seniors, without considering their constitution. But the constitution may vary from being completely healthy to invalidity. For the product development the age is not as important as the state of health and some other parameters that influence the use of technical devices. On the one hand physical and mental abilities can play an important role in how a product is used or whether it is considered as useful or not. On the other hand the familiarization to technical products in general, which is influenced by professional life and social environment impact the use of technical products and their acceptance as well (Lang et al., 2011).

In order to develop a product that is able to support seniors in their daily life, not only their needs, but also their criteria for acceptance have to be considered. A product that does not fulfill the technical requirements cannot support the user. But an unaccepted product that fulfills all the technical requirements does not either. The aspects

that influence both requirements and acceptance are shown in figure 1.

Figure 1 Influences on the system's functionality and design (Paetzold, 2011)

Obviously, accessibility that influences the system's functionality, and usability that influences design and ergonomics have to be considered. The heterogeneity of the user group has to be taken into account for the acceptance as well. The acceptance of a very dissimilar group has to be predicted by a relatively small group of users. One objective of this research project is to find out, how the sample has to be structured to get adequate results. Both acceptance and requirements have to be controlled at different points of time in the product development process. Only if they are controlled continuously, the product will fulfill the requirements and will finally be accepted. The methods for the integration of the users and the measurement of acceptance have to be chosen according to the status of the development process. The product presentation to the users and hence the choice of usable methods depends on the available data. But the context of the usage and the kind of product influence the choice of the method as well. The context changes whether the product is an everyday product that is used by everyone, like a phone, or a special aid that is used only by disabled people. Even aspects like usage at home or outside or whether it is a portable device or not may change both criteria of acceptance and the appropriate method for measurement. As described in Lang et al. (2011), the methods of integration of users have to be adapted to the special characteristics of elderly users.

MODULAR DESIGN APPROACHES

The heterogeneity of seniors as one user group mentioned above and the wide range of requirements resulting can be faced with the methods of modular design. There are approaches for modular design e.g. from Pimmler & Eppinger (1994) or Erixon (1996). These approaches have to be extended in order to design products that fulfill most of these various requirements. The product has to be adapted to the user's needs when it is bought. Modular design offers the possibility that each sub-function is realized in one module. All the functions that the user needs can be combined by adding the appropriate module. But not only the number of functions is variable, even the realization of each function is. The output of a warning signal, for example, can be adapted to the capability of the user. It can be a visual, audible or haptic signal. The function "warning output" does not change, but the way how it is done varies.

The second advantage is the adaptability of the modular product during its useful life. If the interfaces are designed properly, the modules can be changed and hence the product can be adapted anytime. This is a special advantage for people suffering from age-related disabilities, as these typically change gradually or additional ones occur. This changes the users' abilities and hence their needs which influence the product requirements. Increasing visual impairment, for example, requires the adaptation of displays. Therefore, the module that contains the display should be variable, in order to adapt the function in a first step to the decreasing capability. This could be done by magnifying the letters in the display or by changing contrast or brightness of the display. If this is not sufficient anymore the module has to be replaced by another one, which fulfills the same function in a different way that the user can handle again. In this example it could be an enlarged display. If this is no longer sufficient, another module, which fulfills the function in a completely different way, is needed. The output of signals can be changed from visual into acoustic or vice versa in case of hearing impairment. Modular design permits the variety of functions. They can be added or left out, if this is helpful due to the disabilities. A walker or Zimmer frame can be taken as an example for the addition of functions. If the

user singly has difficulty in walking, a normal walker fulfills the needs. One possible additional function is a route guidance system, which can be added if cognitive restrictions occur and the user loses orientation. The system leads the user home, if getting lost during a walk or shows the way to the doctor or elsewhere. The user must not be accompanied by somebody else, as long as the route guidance system is understood. If the user does not suffer from cognitive restrictions, but often visits strange cities, the route guidance system can be added right from the start and help to make the user's everyday life easier.

In order to use these advantages of modular design in the development of products for disabled people, the existing approaches have to be adapted to the special constraints. The approach by Pimmler & Eppinger (1994) describes a technical perception to the product. The criteria for defining a module are the interactions between the elements of the product. Elements that strongly interact are clustered to one module. The reduced interaction between different modules simplifies the interface design. For the exchangeability of the modules it is important to reduce the influence between the modules as far as possible. Above all it is easier to develop new modules if they are not or little influenced by the other ones and do not influence them neither.

Erixon's (1996) approach on the other side is more economic. He describes the Module Indication Matrix, which relates the elements to module drivers. The module drivers permit to estimate the benefit, if an element is designed as a module. It is easy to extend this approach with the requirements due to the disabilities. As a module driver both the adaptability at the purchase and the adaptability during useful life can be regarded.

For the development of products for disabled people a combination of both approaches is needed. The exchangeability of the modules needs properly designed interfaces and the module drivers help to understand which elements are useful modules at all.

DISABILITIES IN PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT

In order to offer optimum support for people with age-related disabilities it is useful to create products with three steps of support:

- motivation to use
- support to use
- compensation of disabilities.

This trisection differentiates an inclusive design product from an aid for disabled people. This difference is shown in figure 2. An optimum inclusive design product offers the same support to everybody, no matter if the user is disabled or not. A poor designed standard product offers support for able-bodied people, but this support decreases with increasing disability. On the contrary, the support offered by an optimum adaptable product increases with increasing disability. That way the user gets exactly as much support as needed.

In order to adapt products to the user's changing capability a product should be able to provide all of the three steps.

At the purchase of the product it is adapted to the

user's needs. The restrictions that are obvious and the user's wishes are regarded at this moment and the product functions are added appropriately. The user gets a product that fits the needs ideally at the time of purchase. Changing needs due to changing disabilities or a different environment have to be considered when they occur. It is crucial to support the user as much as needed, but not more. Abilities that are still there but not used will decrease. The product should exercise all these abilities and support the user if they are missing. Especially the compensation of lost abilities should not start until the product cannot be used any longer without it. Not until visual impairment for example is so strong, that the information cannot be noticed, information that is normally provided in a display should be provided by sound or haptic signals. For the example of the walker this means, that the first step of motivation is a walker designed with the criteria of inclusive design. It enables the user to walk but nothing more. If an additional disability occurs, such as decreasing muscular strength, an

Figure 2. Difference between Inclusive Design and adaptable product (Höfner, 2011)

electric motor is added. This can help the user to push the walker uphill if the own strength is not sufficient any more. Then it is possible to use the walker even if the disability would permit to use a normal one.

Additional cognitive restrictions, like dementia, may require a route guidance system, which shows the user the way in case of being lost. If the cognitive impairment becomes worse and the user cannot cope with the instructions of the route guidance system this can be connected with the electric motor. Then the walker drives home independently and the user just has to hold the handle bar and follow it. The walker compensates the cognitive restrictions in this state. Obviously, some more elements like sensors are needed in this case.

INTEGRATION INTO THE PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT PROCESS

The aspects of modular design and the integration of users as mentioned above have to be comprehensible to the design engineer. They can only be used if the application is understood. In order to ensure this, these methods have to be included into the product development process. The FORFLOW process model (FFPM) is appropriate there, because the development process is structured very detailed, into almost 90 steps (Krehmer, et. al., 2009). Due to the detailed structure the status of the available data is known for each step and a set of applicable methods of user participation can be attached. It is not possible to definitely link one method to one step as the appropriate method depends on various aspects, not only the progress in the development process. It is context-sensitive. The kind of product that is developed has an impact, but the constitution of the user group that participates and the usage conditions of the product influence the choice of the method as well.

The methods for user participation are linked to the steps in the FFPM when the participation is useful and the data available is sufficient for the use of the method. Each method is described with its advantages and disadvantages, which are depending on the boundary restrictions. The design engineer can use this list of methods linked to each step and choose the method that is best for the active project.

Beside the integration of users the approaches of modular design are linked to the FFPM as well. First the steps where modular design has to be taken into account are identified. The main function of the product has to be identified, because the product has to definitely fulfill this function. Therefore, the main function is not realized in a module. By means of the modular design approaches, it has to be identified which of the sub-functions are realized as a module and which are not. These steps can be marked in the FFPM and the design engineer can systematically work them off. Beside this, the step to which all modules are developed can be defined. After the specification of the interfaces it is not essential to develop all the modules. Some of them may never be asked for by the user and in order to save time and money during the development, they do not have to be completely designed. This makes the development of the basic version of the product both cheaper and faster. The other modules are developed if asked for.

But the methods of user participation and modular design have to be linked together as well, as they influence each other. On the one hand the results of the user participation influence the design of the modules. If the user participation shows that one module is not considered as useful, this module will not be developed or the development will be stopped. On the other hand the development progress of the module will influence the appropriate method for user participation and as the progress can vary between the modules the modules have to be evaluated by using different methods. In order to develop adaptable and accepted products, that support seniors in their everyday life it is crucial to link these methods together.

SUMMARY AND OUTLOOK

This approach for the development of products for age-related disabled people is meant to support the design engineer in the development of products that fulfill the users' needs. Hence, both disabilities and individual attitude have to be translated into technical requirements. There the methods of user integration are appropriate. In order to adapt the products to the changing disabilities they have to be designed modular. Both approaches have to be

included in one, in order to consider both disabilities and acceptance in the development process.

The next step in this project is to evaluate this approach within the development of a walker. It is planned to provide a walker with an additional electric motor in order to support the user uphill. As another additional function the walker will be equipped with a route guidance system. A likewise route guidance system is described by Paetzold (2011). The experience of this former project will be transferred to the active one. This route guidance system can be used like a normal one, known from cars, or it can be connected to the motor and independently lead users with severe cognitive impairment. The integration of sensors to detect barriers will help users with visual impairment. All these functions are developed via integration of users and their acceptance will be monitored during the whole process. The prototype developed this way should fulfill most of the users' needs and be accepted by the majority of potential users. The acceptance of the prototype will be evaluated in order to find out, whether the result from the integration of the users matches the actual acceptance of users, which are not included in the development.

REFERENCES

- Coleman, R., Lebbon, C., Clarkson, J., Keates, S. (2003) From margins to mainstream. In: Clarkson, J., Coleman, R., Keates, S.,
- Lebbon, C. (2003) *Inclusive Design - Design for the whole population*. London, Berlin: Springer, 1-25.
- Erixon, G. (1996) Modular Function Deployment (MFD), Support for Good Product Structure Creation. In: *Proceeding of the 2nd WDK Workshop on Product Structuring*, June 3-4, 1996, Delft, Holland.
- Herwig, O. (2008) *Universal design - Solutions for a barrier-free living*. Basel: Birkhäuser
- Hoffmann, E. (2007) *Consumer Integration in Sustainable Product Development*. Bus. Stat. Env. Nr. 16. (pp. 322-338)
- Höfner, B. (2011) Information from VDI- Fachausschuss Gerontotechnik. Frankfurt, 13.04.2011
- Krehmer, H., Eckstein, R., Lauer, W., Roelofsen, J., Stöber, C., Troll, A., Weber, N., Zapf, J. (2009) Coping with multidisciplinary product development - a process model approach. In: *Proceedings of the 16th International Conference of Engineering Design (ICED 09)*. August 24-27, 2009, Stanford University, Stanford, CA, USA
- Kujala, S. (2003) User involvement: A review of the benefits and challenges. *Behavior and Information Technology* (pp. 1-16), 22
- Lang, F., Williger, B., Rupprecht, R., Meerkamm, H., Stöber, C. (2011) Fit4Use und Fit4Product - Querschnittsprojekte . In: *FitForAge Abschlussbericht*. Erlangen-Nürnberg, München, Regensburg, Würzburg
- Lindenberger, U., Lövdén, M., Schellenbach, M., Li, S.-C., Krüger, A. (2011) *Psychologische Kriterien für erfolgreiche Alterstechnologien aus Sicht der Lebensspannenkognition*. Nova Acta Leopoldina NF 104, Nr. 368, 17-33
- Paetzold, K. (2011) An Approach to Adapt the Product Functionality to the Ability of Seniors. In: Ziefle, M., Röcker, C. *Human-Centered Design of E-Health Technologies: Concepts, Methods and Applications*. Hershey: IGI-Global, 127-153
- Pimmler, T.U., Eppinger, S.D. (1994) Integration Analysis of Product Decompositions. In: *Proceedings of the ASME Design Theory and Methodology Conference*, September 1994 Minneapolis, MN.
- Sarodnick, F. & Brau, H. (2006) *Methoden der Usability Evaluation - Wissenschaftliche Grundlagen und praktische Anwendungen*. Bern: Huber